

MODERNIZATION OF SPORTS AND RECREATION SPACES IN THE URBAN ENVIRONMENT

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Summary: The article discusses the importance of the formation and modernization of urban pedestrian spaces, and also sports and recreational spaces in the urban environment.

Key words: urban environment, green spaces, sports spaces, workouts.

Modern trends in urbanization and the growth of the urban population, combined with environmental problems, have an impact on the quality of urban life. The problems of overpopulation, building compaction, transport, environmental problems constantly require close attention. In this regard, the World Health Organization in the report "Green spaces in cities and health" called on the authorities of the cities of the world to create as many green spaces as possible. Being in nature allows people to partially compensate for the harmful effects of various factors, such as air pollution, noise and extreme heat.

Residents of many large cities have a special need for physical activity, as people lead a mostly sedentary lifestyle, constantly experiencing high stress on the nervous system. To solve these problems, active rest with certain physical loads is required. For this purpose, both indoor sports facilities and open public spaces of a sports and recreational nature are intended.

The state of human health is the basis of his life, has an impact on the physical, social and moral development of himself, on labor activity, creativity and success. To possess all the above qualities, to strengthen and maintain health, it is necessary to engage in physical culture.

Physical culture seems to be an integral part of the general culture in modern society, as it is represented by a multifaceted comprehensive improvement of the human body through physical exercise, compliance with the correct household and work regime. Physical culture prepares the basis for the formation of health and a healthy lifestyle.

Outdoor sports spaces attract a variety of activities, offering every city dweller a level playing field to pursue an active and healthy lifestyle through the possibility of year-round activities and the creation of new communities around them.

So, in Tashkent there are quite a few sports facilities, both indoor and outdoor. For example, Ice Avenue (sports complex, skating rink), Humo Arena multifunctional ice complex, Yunusabad sports complex, Jar, Yoshlik sports and

recreation complex, Pakhtakor stadium and others. Many of these sports facilities are designed to train professional athletes. There are also facilities for amateurs - various fitness centers, gyms, small indoor swimming pools.

However, in accordance with the decree of the head of state Shavkat Mirziyoyev "On measures for the widespread introduction of a healthy lifestyle and the further development of mass sports", it is currently important to increase pedestrian and bicycle paths, as well as open spaces for sports and recreation activities.

Different age groups of the population influence the formation of spaces based on their respective preferences. Thus, conducting a field analysis of open public spaces in Tashkent, along with good indicators of landscaping, it is possible to identify a number of social issues that have not yet been fully resolved. This is the inconvenience of the environment for various social groups, for example, the lack of convenient areas for people with disabilities. This contributes to the fact that these territories are no longer attractive to people, do not meet the requirements for urban public spaces.

Squares, boulevards, embankments should become zones of psychological rehabilitation in the urban environment. In their planning structure, they should include, first of all, natural means of landscape design in order to achieve a certain directed impact on a person.

As a result of the study, proposals were formulated for the modernization of sports and recreation spaces in the form of a conceptual model. The proposed conceptual model of sports and recreation spaces in the urban environment includes a combination of various "places" for sports.

Yard space - a space within microdistricts, located in close proximity to places of residence, can be represented by workouts (separately for men, separately for women, based on social preferences), a playground for children, a playground for yoga and stretching, badminton and even mini-golf. Serves for daily sports and fitness activities.

Linear space, a space intended for transit traffic, is located on boulevards, alleys, embankments. The linear space is represented by a bicycle path, a walking path and a jogging path. It can be decorated with a multifunctional design (the prototype of which is a graphic representation of the work of the heart), which includes: arches, benches, lighting devices. Infrastructure is developed along the way. It can also be used for daily sports and recreation activities, especially for people who use this area as a transit, walking path, moving to work places, etc.

"Pocket" space - a mini-compact space that can contain different sites (one or two) for a certain type of recreational activities. (In the urbanized environment of the city, pocket parks are the best option for the formation of new public spaces in the context of reconstruction through redevelopment.) Can be used both independently, in the structure of the city (occupying free territories in residential and public areas), and accompany linear space, creating in "pockets" environment for various activities, such as: workout, yoga areas, skate areas, areas of sports equipment for the disabled, areas with sensory areas, etc. It can also be used as a recreation area with the inclusion of small architectural forms.

Compact space (cluster) - usually presented in the form of a sports park with a large number of areas for activities such as football, mini-football, handball, tennis, volleyball, golf. In addition, there will be a skate park, a rope park, training and competition grounds, playgrounds, a swimming pool and bike paths.

A prerequisite is the creation of comfortable conditions in the territories, as well as security: for this, small architectural forms (trade kiosks, benches, fountains, urns), night lighting devices should be actively used. The spaces should be well shaded; for this, tall wide-crown trees serve, which do not disturb the view and ventilation conditions, but create comfortable microclimatic conditions. In addition, it is recommended to plant coniferous vegetation of medium height along the roads to clean the air from dust. To maintain optimal conditions for sustainable development, it is recommended to use energy-saving technologies.

Thus, in the process of modernization of sports and recreational spaces, it is necessary to solve such problems as: ecological and aesthetic harmonization of the architectural environment, humanization of space, achievement of compositional integrity, stylistic unity and artistic expressiveness of the environment.

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